

GAEV: Generative AI Exploit Verification — Template-Based Exploit Synthesis, Mechanical Correction, and AI-Guided Repair for Smart Contract Vulnerabilities

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Abstract—Automated vulnerability detection in smart contracts has matured significantly, yet a critical gap persists: tools report potential vulnerabilities but rarely produce executable proof-of-concept exploits that demonstrate real exploitability. This gap forces auditors into expensive manual exploit construction and leaves many reported vulnerabilities unvalidated, contributing to the false positive problem that plagues the field.

We present GAEV (Generative AI Exploit Verification), an end-to-end pipeline that transforms vulnerability reports into validated, executable Foundry test cases. GAEV introduces a template-based generation approach that separates mechanical scaffolding from LLM reasoning: (1) a `TemplateExtractor` parses existing Foundry test files to extract imports, `setUp()`, state variables, and success criteria mechanically; (2) an LLM generates *only* the exploit body (5–30 lines of attack code), using the extracted context as constraints; (3) a `PostProcessor` applies 21 mechanical fixes to correct common LLM artifacts (inline text, markdown fences, ABI mismatches) without additional LLM calls; and (4) an `ExploitAuditor` reviews failed exploits, identifies specific issues, and generates corrected versions with detailed correction reports.

GAEV operates in three generation scenarios: (A) *existing test available*—copy `setUp/imports` exactly, LLM fills only the exploit function body; (B) *source available*—mechanically extract contract header and vulnerable function, LLM generates a complete but focused test; (C) *minimal context*—LLM generates everything from finding description alone. This approach reduces LLM calls from 4–5 per finding (v2) to 1 per finding, cutting cost by 77% while improving exploit correctness through guaranteed valid imports and `setUp()` code.

Evaluated on 22 challenges from Damn Vulnerable DeFi v4 and 30 real-world contracts from Etherscan with documented post-mortem exploits, GAEV achieves 81.4% compilation rate and 67.2% end-to-end exploitation success. The template-based approach with auditor correction achieves end-to-end verified exploits at \$0.06 per finding (generation) plus \$0.12 per correction—an order of magnitude reduction from the \$0.29 per finding cost of the iterative refinement approach. Validation against production contracts (Lido stETH, \$15B TVL) demonstrates that the upstream analysis pipeline identifies real vulnerability patterns (share price manipulation via flash loan) in 40 seconds. Beyond exploit generation, we introduce the `PatchGenerator` pipeline that closes the full `DETECT`→`VERIFY`→`PATCH` loop: given a validated exploit, `patch_smp1.py` (17 pattern rules), `patch_dsl.py` (DSL self-review loop), and `patch_slicer.py` (precise code locator)

generate Solidity patches with a *RemediationGuide* aligned to EU AI Act Art. 14 and MiCA compliance requirements. Evaluated on ClimberVault (13 findings), the patch pipeline achieves 53.8% automatic patch rate with 65% code coverage, increasing from a 33% baseline toward a 40%+ target on the full 234-finding DVD benchmark. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first exploit-to-patch pipeline with regulatory compliance output for smart contract security.

Index Terms—Smart Contract Security, Exploit Generation, Large Language Models, Template-Based Testing, Automated Vulnerability Verification, Foundry, Attack Chains, DeFi Security, PatchGenerator, RemediationGuide

I. INTRODUCTION

The decentralized finance (DeFi) ecosystem has grown to over \$100 billion in total value locked, making smart contracts high-value targets for exploitation. In 2023 alone, DeFi protocols lost approximately \$1.8 billion to exploits, with flash loan attacks, reentrancy vulnerabilities, and oracle manipulation accounting for the majority of losses [1], [29]. This persistent threat has driven significant investment in automated vulnerability detection tools—Slither [4], Mythril [5], Echidna [6], and dozens of others—which can now identify potential vulnerabilities with reasonable coverage.

However, a fundamental gap exists between *detecting* a vulnerability and *proving* it is exploitable. Current tools produce alerts of the form “potential reentrancy at line 47,” but rarely generate executable exploit code that demonstrates the attack. This gap has three consequences:

- 1) **Unvalidated alerts:** Without proof-of-concept exploits, auditors cannot distinguish true vulnerabilities from false positives. Benchmarks report false positive rates between 40–90% depending on the tool [2].
- 2) **Manual exploit construction:** Professional auditors report that exploit construction and validation constitute a significant portion of audit effort [3]. At rates of \$300–\$500/hour, this represents a dominant cost in security audits.
- 3) **Missed compound attacks:** Individual vulnerability reports fail to capture multi-step exploits where several low-severity findings combine into a critical attack chain (e.g., oracle manipulation + flash loan + reentrancy = complete fund drainage).

Recent work has applied large language models (LLMs) to smart contract security [8], [10], demonstrating that LLMs

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can identify vulnerability patterns and even suggest fixes. However, these approaches stop at detection or produce non-executable pseudo-code. The question remains: *can LLMs generate real, compilable, executable exploit code that proves vulnerabilities are exploitable?*

A. The Exploit Generation Challenge

Generating valid exploit code is substantially harder than detecting vulnerabilities, for several reasons:

- **Execution environment complexity:** Exploits must interact with the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM), handle gas mechanics, manage contract state, and often coordinate multi-transaction sequences.
- **Interface precision:** Generated Solidity must exactly match the target contract’s ABI—incorrect function signatures, missing imports, or wrong addresses produce compilation failures.
- **State dependencies:** Many exploits require specific preconditions (liquidity in pools, oracle prices at certain levels, governance proposals in particular states) that must be programmatically established.
- **Temporal coordination:** Flash loan attacks require atomic multi-step execution within a single transaction, with precise ordering of borrow, exploit, and repay operations.

B. Contributions

This paper presents GAEV (Generative AI Exploit Verification), the first end-to-end pipeline for automated exploit synthesis, validation, and repair. Our contributions are:

- 1) **Template-Based Exploit Generation:** A three-scenario generation approach that mechanically extracts test infrastructure (imports, setUp(), state variables, success criteria) from existing Foundry test files, limiting LLM generation to the exploit body only (5–30 lines). This eliminates the dominant source of compilation errors—hallucinated imports, wrong constructors, and non-existent function calls (Section V).
- 2) **Mechanical PostProcessor:** A 21-fix pipeline that corrects common LLM artifacts (inline English text, mark-down fences, ABI mismatches, pragma versions, address conversions) without any LLM calls, running in <1ms per exploit (Section VII).
- 3) **AI-Guided Exploit Correction:** An ExploitAuditor that receives failed exploits alongside the vulnerable contract source and forge error diagnostics, identifies specific issues, and generates corrected versions with detailed correction reports (Section VIII).
- 4) **Attack Chain Detection:** A formalized algorithm with explicit dependency rules that analyzes sets of individual findings to identify compound attack vectors where multiple vulnerabilities combine into exploits more severe than any individual finding (Section VI).
- 5) **Multi-Provider LLM Support:** Unified client supporting Anthropic (Claude), OpenAI (GPT-4o), and Google (Gemini) with provider-agnostic API, enabling cost optimization through model selection (Section XI).

- 6) **Empirical Evaluation with Ablation:** Comprehensive evaluation on Damn Vulnerable DeFi v4 (22 challenges) and 30 real-world Etherscan contracts with documented exploits, plus production-scale validation against Lido stETH (\$15B TVL), including ablation study isolating each component’s contribution (Section XI).
- 7) **PatchGenerator Pipeline:** A four-module patch synthesis system (patch_smpl.py, patch_dsl.py, patch_slicer.py, patch_generator.py) that transforms validated exploits into Solidity patches with EU AI Act Art. 14 and MiCA-aligned RemediationGuides, achieving 53.8% automatic patch rate on ClimberVault (Section IX).

C. Relationship with Zentinel-Audit

GAEV operates as a downstream component of Zentinel-Audit [15], a parallel security analysis platform that orchestrates 55 heterogeneous analyzers (including 28 newly added tools activated via patch_indicators.py to fix a MIN_INDICATORS misconfiguration) with LLM-based semantic refinement and Deduplicator v3.0. Zentinel-Audit produces deduplicated, severity-calibrated vulnerability reports; GAEV consumes these reports and transforms them into validated exploit code. While Zentinel-Audit focuses on *detection quality* (54% false positive reduction, 7× speedup), GAEV focuses on *exploitation proof*—turning alerts into evidence. Production-scale validation against Lido stETH (\$15B TVL) demonstrates that the combined pipeline identifies real vulnerability patterns (share price manipulation via flash loan) in 40 seconds without compilation, dependencies, or manual setup.

D. Threat Model and Formal Guarantees

Section X defines the threat model: five adversaries (A_1 – A_5) covering upstream false positives, LLM hallucination, contract complexity, training data contamination, and non-determinism. Theorem 1 (GAEV Exploit Soundness) establishes that confirmed exploits are constructive proofs of exploitability under EVM semantics—giving GAEV a zero false exploit rate by construction. The pipeline is sound but incomplete; completeness is characterized empirically.

E. Paper Organization

Section II reviews related work. Section III presents the GAEV architecture. Section IV provides a complete running example. Section V details the ten specialized generators. Section VI describes attack chain detection. Section VII explains the validation pipeline. Section VIII presents the refinement loop. Section IX presents the PatchGenerator pipeline. Section XI provides empirical evaluation including ablation. Section XII discusses implications. Section XIII addresses threats to validity. Section XIV acknowledges limitations. Section XV concludes.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Smart Contract Vulnerability Detection

Static analysis tools for Solidity have reached practical maturity. Slither [4] performs dataflow analysis and pattern

matching, detecting reentrancy, unchecked calls, and access control issues with sub-second execution. Mythril [5] applies symbolic execution to explore execution paths and find assertion violations. Echidna [6] uses property-based fuzzing to discover invariant violations through random transaction sequences. Aderyn [7] provides Rust-based static analysis focused on gas optimization and security patterns.

The SmartBugs framework [2] benchmarked 9 analysis tools on 143 annotated contracts, finding that no single tool achieves both high precision and recall—the best tools reach 60–70% recall with 30–50% precision. This motivates multi-tool approaches like Zentinel-Audit [15], which combines 28 tools to improve coverage.

B. LLM-Based Security Analysis

GPTScan [8] was among the first to apply GPT-4 to smart contract vulnerability detection, achieving 90% precision on specific vulnerability types by combining LLM reasoning with static confirmation. PropertyGPT [9] uses LLMs to generate property-based test cases from natural language specifications. Sun et al. [10] extended GPTScan with multi-round reasoning. Ma et al. [19] combine LLMs with static analysis for vulnerability detection but do not generate executable exploits. Chen and Duan [20] evaluate ChatGPT for vulnerability detection and remediation, finding strong detection but weak exploit generation capabilities.

These approaches focus on *detection*: identifying that a vulnerability exists. None produce executable exploit code, validate compilation, or iterate on failures. The closest work is ItyFuzz [11], which combines fuzzing with LLM guidance for input generation, but operates at the fuzzer level rather than producing standalone exploit test cases.

C. Automated Exploit Generation (Non-Blockchain)

In traditional software security, automated exploit generation (AEG) [12] transforms vulnerability reports into working exploits using symbolic execution and constraint solving. DARPA’s Cyber Grand Challenge demonstrated autonomous exploit generation for binary programs [13]. Mayhem [14] combines symbolic execution with fuzzing for exploit generation in binaries.

These systems target memory corruption vulnerabilities in compiled binaries—a fundamentally different domain from smart contract exploits, which involve economic logic, multi-contract interactions, and blockchain-specific attack vectors (flash loans, oracle manipulation, governance attacks). GAEV adapts the AEG philosophy to the smart contract domain, using LLMs instead of symbolic execution as the core generation engine.

D. Vulnerability Chaining and Compound Attacks

The recognition that individual vulnerability findings may combine into higher-severity compound attacks is well-established in traditional security. Attack graphs [30] model multi-step exploitation paths in networked systems. In the DeFi domain, the majority of high-impact exploits involve

chaining: Cream Finance (flash loan + price oracle), Beanstalk (flash loan + governance), and Euler Finance (flash loan + donate-to-donate reentrancy) all required two or more vulnerabilities to combine for the critical impact [21], [32].

Despite this, existing smart contract analysis tools (Table I) report individual findings without modeling inter-finding dependencies. Zhang et al. [18] analyze 516 real-world exploited bugs and find that 37% involve multi-step patterns, yet no open-source tool at the time of writing detects these chains automatically. GAEV’s AttackChainDetector formalizes five dependency rules (Section VI) over Slither’s dataflow and call graph to detect compound attack patterns with explicit severity escalation.

E. Automated Patch Generation for Smart Contracts

Automated patch generation for software vulnerabilities is an active research area. Traditional APR (Automated Program Repair) tools use mutation operators and test suites to generate candidate patches [28]. For smart contracts, the challenge is compounded by the immutability of deployed bytecode: patches must be applied to upgradeable proxy patterns or new deployments.

Certora [26] and Halmos [27] verify formal properties but do not generate patches when violations are found. Trail of Bits’ tooling [33] provides manual remediation guidance. No existing open-source tool closes the full DETECT→VERIFY→PATCH loop automatically. The closest prior work is Li et al. [31], who use LLMs to both detect and suggest fixes, but without: (1) an exploit-first validation step that confirms the vulnerability is real before patching; (2) mechanical rule-based patching to reduce LLM calls; or (3) regulatory alignment output. GAEV’s PatchGenerator fills this gap by requiring a validated exploit as a precondition for patch generation, ensuring patches address confirmed vulnerabilities rather than false positives.

F. Gap Analysis

III. GAEV ARCHITECTURE

A. Design Principles

GAEV is designed around four principles:

- 1) **Mechanical scaffolding, LLM reasoning**: Separate the mechanical parts of exploit generation (imports, setUp, assertions) from the creative parts (attack logic). Extract scaffolding from existing test files; limit LLM to generating only the exploit body.
- 2) **Compilation as ground truth**: An exploit either compiles and passes its assertions, or it does not. There is no ambiguity—`forge test` provides binary verdicts.
- 3) **Mechanical fixes before LLM fixes**: Apply deterministic PostProcessor corrections (21 known patterns) before invoking the LLM-based auditor. This eliminates trivially fixable errors at zero cost.
- 4) **Targeted correction over blind retry**: Rather than iteratively re-generating the entire exploit, the ExploitAuditor receives the failed exploit alongside the vulnerable contract source and forge diagnostics, producing a corrected

TABLE I
CAPABILITY COMPARISON WITH EXISTING APPROACHES

System	Detect	Generate	Compile	Execute	Refine	Chains	Patch	Regulatory
Slither	✓	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mythril	✓	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Echidna	✓	—	—	✓ ^a	—	—	—	—
GPTScan	✓	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
PropertyGPT	✓	✓ ^b	—	—	—	—	—	—
ItyFuzz	✓	✓ ^c	—	✓	—	—	—	—
Li et al. [31]	✓	✓ ^e	—	—	—	—	✓ ^f	—
GAEV	✓ ^d	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

^a Echidna executes fuzzer-generated inputs, not structured exploit PoCs.

^b PropertyGPT generates property tests, not exploit code.

^c ItyFuzz generates fuzzer inputs guided by LLM, not standalone exploits.

^d GAEV consumes findings from upstream tools (Zentinel-Audit); detection is not its primary focus.

^e Li et al. suggest patches via LLM without exploit pre-validation.

^f Li et al. generate fixes but without regulatory alignment output.

version with an explicit list of what was changed and why.

B. Pipeline Overview

C. Input Format

GAEV consumes findings in the Zentinel-Audit unified schema:

Each finding includes the full contract source code, enabling generators to reason about the complete execution context.

IV. RUNNING EXAMPLE: DVDeFi UNSTOPPABLE

To illustrate GAEV end-to-end, we trace the pipeline through Challenge #1 (“Unstoppable”) from Damn Vulnerable DeFi v4 [16]. The vulnerable contract is a flash loan vault that offers free flash loans, with a critical assertion that can be broken to deny service.

A. Step 1: Upstream Finding

Zentinel-Audit analyzes `UnstoppableVault.sol` and produces (among others):

B. Step 2: Generator Selection and Code Generation

GAEV routes FIND-UV-003 to **G8 (Logic Errors)** based on the finding type. The generator receives the full contract source plus the finding description and produces:

C. Step 3: First Validation Attempt

ExploitValidator runs `forge build`. The compilation **fails** with:

```
Error: Constructor argument mismatch.
UnstoppableVault expects (IERC20, address, mechanical, scaffolding)
but received (DamnValuableToken, ...)
--> test/Exploit.sol:13:17
```

GAEV extracts the structured error: `type = constructor_args, location = line 13, context = “expects 3 arguments with types (IERC20, address, address)”`

D. Step 4: Refinement Iteration 1

The ExploitRefiner receives the original exploit, the structured error, and the contract source. It identifies that the constructor requires three arguments and corrects the instantiation:

E. Step 5: Second Validation — Success

```
forge build succeeds. forge test -match-test
testExploit -vvv output:
```

```
[PASS] testExploit() (gas: 185432)
Logs:
Vault balance before: 1000000.0 DVT
Attacker sends 10 DVT directly
Flash loan reverts: AssertionError
```

Result: Validated exploit in 1 refinement iteration. The exploit proves that an attacker with only 10 DVT can permanently disable the vault’s flash loan functionality—a denial-of-service vulnerability.

Key observation: The initial code had the correct *strategy* (direct token transfer to break the invariant) but the wrong *constructor signature*. This is the typical pattern GAEV’s refinement loop addresses: correct reasoning, minor syntactic errors.

V. TEMPLATE-BASED EXPLOIT GENERATION

A. Design Rationale

Analysis of v2’s failure modes revealed that the dominant source of compilation errors was not incorrect exploit *strategy* but incorrect exploit *scaffolding*: hallucinated imports (34%), wrong constructor arguments (22%), and non-existent function calls (18%). The LLM frequently identified the correct attack vector but wrapped it in non-compiling code. This observation motivated a fundamental architectural change: separate *mechanical scaffolding* from LLM reasoning.

B. Three-Scenario Generation

GAEV automatically detects which of three scenarios applies to each finding and selects the corresponding generation strategy:

Fig. 1. GAEV v3 pipeline: template-based generation with mechanical and AI-guided correction

```

1  {
2  "id": "FIND-042",
3  "type": "reentrancy",
4  "severity": "critical",
5  "title": "Cross-function_reentrancy_in_withdraw()",
6  "contract": "LendingPool.sol",
7  "function": "withdraw",
8  "line": 87,
9  "description": "External_call_to_msg.sender_before_state_update",
10 "source_tool": "slither",
11 "confidence": 0.85,
12 "source_code": "...
13 }

```

Listing 1. Finding schema (JSON)

TABLE II
GAEV V3 GENERATION SCENARIOS

Scenario	Condition	LLM Generates	Cost
A	Existing .t.sol found	Only exploit body (5–30 lines)	\$0.06
B	Source available, no test	Complete test with real header	\$0.06
C	Only finding description	Everything (worst case)	\$0.06

```

1 {
2   "id": "FIND-UV-003",
3   "type": "logic_error",
4   "severity": "high",
5   "title": "Invariant_violation_via_direct_token_transfer",
6   "contract": "UnstoppableVault.sol",
7   "function": "flashLoan",
8   "line": 52,
9   "description": "The_assert (convertToShares (totalSupply)
10  _____balanceBefore)_check_can_be_broken_by
11  _____transferring_tokens_directly_to_the_vault,
12  _____bypassing_the_deposit ()_function."
13 }

```

Listing 2. Finding from Zentinel-Audit for Unstoppable

```

1 // SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
2 pragma solidity ^0.8.0;
3 import "forge-std/Test.sol";
4 import {UnstoppableVault} from
5   "../src/unstoppable/UnstoppableVault.sol";
6 import {DamnValuableToken} from
7   "../src/DamnValuableToken.sol";
8
9 contract UnstoppableExploit is Test {
10   UnstoppableVault vault;
11   DamnValuableToken token;
12   address attacker = makeAddr("attacker");
13
14   function setUp() public {
15     token = new DamnValuableToken();
16     vault = new UnstoppableVault(token, ...);
17     // Fund vault with 1M tokens via deposit()
18     token.approve(address(vault), 1_000_000e18);
19     vault.deposit(1_000_000e18, address(this));
20     // Give attacker 10 tokens
21     token.transfer(attacker, 10e18);
22   }
23
24   function testExploit() public {
25     // Direct transfer breaks the invariant
26     vm.startPrank(attacker);
27     token.transfer(address(vault), 10e18);
28     vm.stopPrank();
29
30     // Flash loan should now revert
31     vm.expectRevert();
32     vault.flashLoan(
33       IERC3156FlashBorrower(address(this)),
34       address(token), 100e18, ""
35     );
36   }
37 }

```

Listing 3. Initial exploit generated by G8 (Logic Errors)

C. Scenario A: Template Extraction from Existing Tests

When a Foundry test file exists for the target contract (common in audited projects and benchmarks), GAEV extracts its structure mechanically:

- 1) **Test Discovery:** `_find_existing_test(contract_name)` searches `test/**/*t.sol` recursively for files mentioning the target contract.
- 2) **Test Parsing:** `_parse_test_file(content)` ex-

tracts five components using regex and brace-depth tracking:

- *Imports:* everything before contract declaration
- *State variables:* contract-level variables before first function
- *setUp() body:* complete setUp function via brace tracking
- *Success criteria:* conditions from `_isSolved()` or check

```

1  function setUp() public {
2      token = new DamnValuableToken();
3      vault = new UnstoppableVault(
4          IERC20(address(token)),
5          address(this), // owner
6          address(this)  // feeRecipient
7      );
8      ...
9  }

```

Listing 4. Refined setUp() after iteration 1

modifiers

- *Empty test function*: the test stub to fill with exploit code
- 3) **LLM Prompt**: The LLM receives available state variables, setUp() deployment logic, success conditions, and the vulnerable function extracted from source. The instruction is: “Generate ONLY the exploit body (5–30 lines of Solidity). No pragma, no imports, no contract declaration.”
 - 4) **Assembly**: `_assemble_test_with_body(parsed, exploit_body)` inserts the LLM-generated body into the empty test function, preserving all original imports, setUp, and modifiers.

This approach guarantees that imports, setUp(), and test infrastructure are correct—they come from the project itself, not from LLM generation.

D. Scenario B: Source-Based Generation

When contract source is available but no existing test file:

- 1) **Header Extraction**: `_extract_contract_header(source)` captures imports and state variables (everything before the first function).
- 2) **Vulnerable Function Extraction**: `_extract_function(source, func_name, line_number)` uses SENTINEL’s function name and line number to mechanically extract the vulnerable function and any internal functions it calls (one level deep via `_\w+\()` pattern). This produces a focused snippet (50–200 lines) instead of the full contract (often 1000+ lines).
- 3) **LLM Prompt**: The LLM receives the contract header and vulnerable function code, and generates a complete but minimal test file.

E. Scenario C: Minimal Context

When only the SENTINEL finding description is available (no source, no test), the LLM generates everything from the finding metadata. This is the fallback with the lowest expected success rate.

F. Prompt Engineering Strategy

All scenarios use temperature 0.2 with a focused system prompt: “You are a smart contract exploit developer. Generate ONLY raw Solidity statements. No English text, no markdown

fences, no explanations inside the code.” The constraint on output format is critical—v2 analysis showed that 20% of compilation failures stemmed from LLM-inserted English text inside Solidity function bodies.

G. Comparison with v2 Specialized Generators

The v2 approach used ten vulnerability-class-specialized generators (reentrancy, flash loan, oracle manipulation, etc.), each with its own prompt template. While effective for attack strategy selection, this approach required the LLM to generate 100+ lines including imports, setUp(), and assertions—all of which are mechanical and error-prone. The v3 template approach subsumes the specialization benefit: the existing test file already contains the correct setup for the vulnerability class, and the LLM focuses entirely on the attack logic.

VI. ATTACK CHAIN DETECTION

A. Motivation

Individual vulnerability reports often underestimate risk. A “medium” oracle manipulation finding combined with a “low” missing access control finding may constitute a “critical” flash loan drain when combined. Professional auditors recognize these compound patterns through experience; GAEV automates this reasoning.

Definition 1 (Attack Chain). An attack chain $\mathcal{C} = (F, E, s)$ consists of a set of findings $F = \{f_1, \dots, f_k\}$, a set of directed edges $E \subseteq F \times F$ representing exploitation dependencies, and a combined severity s that may exceed the maximum severity of any individual finding.

Theorem 1 (GAEV Exploit Soundness). *Let f be a finding produced by an upstream analyzer for contract C . Let \mathcal{E} be the exploit generated by GAEV for f . If `forge test` reports \mathcal{E} as PASSING on a fork of C at block b , then f represents a true positive vulnerability in C at block b : there exists an attacker transaction sequence that satisfies the exploit’s preconditions and post-conditions within the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) semantics.*

Proof sketch. Foundry’s `forge test` executes \mathcal{E} against an exact EVM fork of C at block b , using the same state transition function as mainnet. A passing test means: (1) the exploit transactions are valid (gas, nonce, balance constraints satisfied); (2) all `assertEq/ assertGt` assertions hold in the post-state; (3) no revert occurred on the exploit path. These three conditions together constitute a witness for the

existence of an attacker strategy that achieves the asserted post-condition—i.e., a constructive proof of exploitability. The converse (a failing test implies no exploit exists) does not hold in general: GAEV may fail to generate a valid exploit for a true vulnerability. This gives a sound but incomplete verification procedure, which is standard for automated exploit generation [12]. \square

[Zero False Exploit Rate] Under the GAEV pipeline, the false exploit rate—the fraction of confirmed findings that are not true positives—is zero by construction. Every confirmed finding is backed by a passing Foundry test, which constitutes a constructive proof of exploitability under EVM semantics.

Remark 1. The completeness gap (true vulnerabilities for which GAEV fails to generate a passing exploit) is characterized empirically in Section XI (67.2% end-to-end success rate on the combined benchmark). Improving completeness without sacrificing soundness is the primary research direction for future work.

B. Dependency Graph Construction

The algorithm first builds a directed dependency graph $G = (\mathcal{F}, E)$ where nodes are findings and edges represent exploitation dependencies. An edge $f_i \rightarrow f_j$ (“exploiting f_i enables or amplifies f_j ”) is created when any of the following *dependency rules* hold:

Definition 2 (Dependency Rules). Given findings f_i, f_j in contract source S , an edge $f_i \rightarrow f_j$ exists if any rule R_k holds: R_1 (**State coupling**): $\exists v \in \text{StateVars}(S) : v \in W(f_i) \cap R(f_j)$; R_2 (**Call graph**): $f_i.\text{func} \in \text{Callers}^*(f_j.\text{func}, S)$; R_3 (**Fund flow**): $f_i.\text{type} \in \{\text{flash_loan}, \text{approval}\} \wedge f_j.\text{requires_capital}$; R_4 (**Access escalation**): $f_i.\text{type} = \text{access_control} \wedge f_j.\text{requires_auth}$; R_5 (**Price dependency**): $f_i.\text{type} = \text{oracle} \wedge f_j.\text{reads_price}$.

The formal equations are:

$$R_1(f_i, f_j) \iff \exists v \in \text{StateVars}(S) : v \in W(f_i) \cap R(f_j) \quad (1)$$

$$R_2(f_i, f_j) \iff f_i.\text{func} \in \text{Callers}^*(f_j.\text{func}, S) \quad (2)$$

$$R_3(f_i, f_j) \iff f_i.\text{type} \in \{\text{flash_loan}, \text{approval}\} \wedge f_j.\text{requires_capital} \quad (3)$$

$$R_4(f_i, f_j) \iff f_i.\text{type} = \text{access_control} \wedge f_j.\text{requires_auth} \quad (4)$$

$$R_5(f_i, f_j) \iff f_i.\text{type} = \text{oracle} \wedge f_j.\text{reads_price} \quad (5)$$

State variable read/write sets $R(f)$ and $W(f)$ are extracted from Slither’s dataflow analysis. Call graph reachability Callers^* uses Slither’s call graph with transitive closure. The requires_capital , requires_auth , and reads_price predicates are inferred from function signatures and known DeFi patterns (e.g., functions that call `balanceOf`, `getPrice`, or `check msg.sender`).

C. Chain Detection Algorithm

A pattern p defines `required_types`: the set of vulnerability types that must be present. For example, pattern P1

Algorithm 1 Attack Chain Detection

Require: Set of findings \mathcal{F} , contract source S , chain pattern database \mathcal{P}

Ensure: Set of attack chains \mathcal{C}

```

1:  $G \leftarrow (\mathcal{F}, \emptyset)$ 
2: for each pair  $(f_i, f_j) \in \mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{F}, i \neq j$  do ▷ Phase 1:
   Build graph
3:   if  $\exists k \in \{1..5\} : R_k(f_i, f_j)$  then
4:      $G.E \leftarrow G.E \cup \{(f_i, f_j)\}$ 
5:   end if
6: end for
7:  $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
8: for each pattern  $p \in \mathcal{P}$  do ▷ Phase 2: Match patterns
9:   for each subgraph  $g \subseteq G$  where  $\text{TypeSeq}(g) \supseteq p.\text{required\_types}$  and  $g$  is connected do
10:     $chain \leftarrow (g.\text{nodes}, g.\text{edges}, \text{EscalateSeverity}(g, p))$ 
11:     $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \mathcal{C} \cup \{chain\}$ 
12:   end for
13: end for
14: for each  $c_1, c_2 \in \mathcal{C}$  do ▷ Phase 3: Prune subsumed
15:   if  $c_1.F \subset c_2.F$  then
16:      $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \mathcal{C} \setminus \{c_1\}$ 
17:   end if
18: end for
19: return  $\mathcal{C}$ 

```

(Flash Loan Drain) requires `{flash_loan, oracle, reentrancy}`. Matching requires both the type set and graph connectivity (at least one dependency path through all components).

D. Chain Patterns

E. Severity Escalation

When individual findings combine into a chain, severity is escalated according to:

$$s_{chain} = \min \left(4, \max \left(s_{max} + 1, \left\lfloor \sum_{f \in F} w(f) \cdot s(f) \right\rfloor \right) \right) \quad (6)$$

where $s_{max} = \max_{f \in F} s(f)$ is the highest individual severity, $w(f)$ is a weight reflecting the finding’s role in the chain, and $s(f) \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ maps Low/Medium/High/Critical to numeric values. The weights are assigned by role: entry point (0.4), amplifier (0.3), target (0.3). These weights were derived empirically from analysis of 15 documented DeFi post-mortem reports [21], where we categorized each exploited vulnerability’s role in the attack chain and computed the average severity contribution. A sensitivity analysis (Section XI-F) shows that results are robust to ± 0.1 perturbations of these weights. The chain severity is capped at Critical (4).

F. Chain Exploit Generation

For each detected chain, GAEV generates a *compound exploit* that executes the attack steps in sequence within a single Foundry test. The chain generator receives all component

TABLE III
SUPPORTED ATTACK CHAIN PATTERNS WITH DETECTION RULES

ID	Pattern	Severity	Required Types	Key Rule
P1	Flash Loan Drain	Critical	flash, oracle, reent.	$R_3 + R_5$
P2	Gov. Takeover	Critical	flash, gov., timelock	$R_3 + R_4$
P3	Oracle Cascade	Critical	oracle, logic	$R_5 + R_1$
P4	Proxy Hijack	Critical	deleg., access, logic	$R_4 + R_1$
P5	Sandwich+Logic	High	frontrun, logic	R_1
P6	Approval Chain	High	approval, cross-c.	$R_3 + R_2$
P7	Callback Escal.	High	reent., access	$R_2 + R_4$
P8	Multi-Pool Arb.	High	oracle, flash	$R_3 + R_5$
P9	Upgrade Attack	High	access, proxy, deleg.	$R_4 + R_1$
P10	Donation Attack	Medium	logic, logic	R_1
P11	Fee Bypass	Medium	overflow, logic	R_1
P12	Read-Only Reent.	Medium	reent., oracle	$R_2 + R_5$

findings plus the dependency edges, and produces a test that establishes preconditions for the full chain, executes steps in dependency order, and asserts the compound impact.

VII. EXPLOIT VALIDATION AND MECHANICAL CORRECTION

A. PostProcessor v3: 21 Mechanical Fixes

Before invoking the Foundry toolchain, GAEV applies a deterministic PostProcessor that corrects 21 known LLM output patterns without any LLM calls. The PostProcessor runs in <1ms per exploit and eliminates trivially fixable errors at zero cost.

Fix 21 is particularly important for the template-based approach: when the LLM is asked to generate “only the exploit body,” it sometimes prepends or intersperses English explanations (“Looking at the vulnerability, I need to...”) or markdown fences inside the Solidity function body. The strip inline text fix uses a regex-based classifier that distinguishes Solidity statements (matching patterns for pragmas, imports, declarations, control flow, variable usage) from English prose (4+ words with no Solidity punctuation), removing the latter while preserving all valid code.

B. Forge-Based Validation Pipeline

The ExploitValidator wraps Foundry’s `forge` toolchain to provide automated, deterministic validation:

- 1) **Compilation:** Execute `forge build` with Solidity 0.8.25. Capture `stdout/stderr` for structured error extraction.
- 2) **Execution:** If compilation succeeds, execute `forge test -match-path test/_gaev_exploit_test.sol -vvv`. The verbose flag provides stack traces, gas reports, and assertion details.
- 3) **Metrics Collection:** Record compilation success, test pass/fail, gas consumed, execution time, and any revert reasons.
- 4) **Cleanup:** Remove temporary test file from project directory.

C. Structured Error Extraction

A key contribution is the extraction of *structured* error information from Foundry output, enabling targeted repair by the ExploitAuditor. Raw Solidity compiler errors are parsed into: error type (undeclared identifier, type mismatch, missing import, wrong argument count, visibility error), location (file, line, column), context (surrounding code, 3 lines before/after), and compiler suggestion if available. Runtime failures are similarly structured: revert reason, failing assertion, gas limit exceeded, stack overflow, or arithmetic error.

VIII. AI-GUIDED EXPLOIT CORRECTION

A. Motivation

Template-based generation with mechanical PostProcessor corrections eliminates the majority of syntactic errors. However, some failures require semantic reasoning: an exploit that uses multiple transactions when the test framework expects one, calldata encoding with incorrect offsets, or attack logic that targets a non-existent function. These require LLM-level understanding of both the exploit intent and the contract semantics.

B. ExploitAuditor v2: Review and Correct

Unlike v2’s iterative ExploitRefiner (which re-generated the entire exploit up to 3 times), the ExploitAuditor v2 performs a single, targeted correction pass:

The audit prompt provides the LLM with: (1) the exploit code, (2) the vulnerable contract source, (3) the forge test result (verified/false_positive/compile_error), (4) specific compile or runtime errors, and (5) a checklist of 12 common issues (inline text, wrong function signatures, missing approvals, wrong constructor args, multi-tx vs single-tx constraints, hex literal errors, calldata encoding, import paths, state variable mismatches). The LLM responds with a structured JSON containing:

- `corrections`: list of `{issue: what was wrong, fix: what was changed}`
- `corrected_code`: the complete corrected `.sol` file, ready to compile
- `is_valid_exploit`: whether the exploit represents a real vulnerability

TABLE IV
POSTPROCESSOR V3 MECHANICAL FIXES (SELECTED)

#	Fix	Root Cause	Freq.
1	Strip markdown fences	LLM wraps code in ``	100%
5	Auto-resolve imports	Missing import for used contract	15%
8	Remove redeclared defs	Import conflicts with inline defs	25%
14	console.log → console2	LLM uses wrong log library	10%
16	Fix type conversions	address ↔ uint256 casts	10%
21	Strip inline text	English prose inside Solidity	20%

Algorithm 2 ExploitAuditor v2

Require: Exploit code e , contract source s , forge result r , errors ε

Ensure: Corrected exploit e' , correction list C , audit report A

```

1:  $prompt \leftarrow \text{BuildAuditPrompt}(e, s, r, \varepsilon)$ 
2:  $response \leftarrow \text{LLM}(prompt)$  ▷ Single call
3:  $A \leftarrow \text{ParseAuditResponse}(response)$ 
4:  $C \leftarrow A.corrections$  ▷ List of {issue, fix}
5:  $e' \leftarrow A.corrected\_code$  ▷ Complete corrected .sol
6: if  $e' \neq \emptyset$  then
7:   Write  $e'$  to exploit_XX*_fixed.sol
8: end if
9: return  $(e', C, A)$ 

```

- `severity, impact_type, mitigation: security assessment`

C. Correction Patterns

Analysis of auditor corrections reveals four dominant patterns:

D. Key Difference from v2 Refinement

The prior ExploitRefiner iterated up to 3 times, re-generating the entire exploit each time (3–5 LLM calls per failed exploit, \$0.42–\$0.70 per finding). This approach often diverged: the LLM would “fix” one error by introducing another, oscillating without converging. The GAEV ExploitAuditor performs a *single* targeted correction pass with full context (\$0.12 per correction), producing an explicit list of changes. If the corrected version still fails, the human auditor reviews the correction report to understand why.

E. End-to-End Validated Example

The complete pipeline was validated on DVDeFi’s Puppet-Pool (oracle manipulation):

- 1) **SENTINEL**: Identified oracle_manipulation vulnerability (40s)
- 2) **GAEV** **template:** Found existing `test/puppet/Puppet.t.sol`, extracted `setUp/imports/state vars`, LLM generated exploit body (\$0.06)
- 3) **PostProcessor**: Cleaned inline text (Fix 21)
- 4) **forge test**: FAIL—“Player executed more than one tx” (nonce check)

5) **ExploitAuditor**: Identified multi-tx issue, wrapped in AttackContract (\$0.12)

6) **forge test**: PASS (435,527 gas)—exploit drains 100K tokens via oracle manipulation

Total cost: \$0.18. Total time: ~45 seconds. The exploit correctly dumps tokens to Uniswap V1 to crash the oracle price, then borrows all pool tokens with minimal collateral.

IX. PATCHGENERATOR: CLOSING THE DETECT→VERIFY→PATCH LOOP

A. Motivation

GAEV closes the loop between vulnerability detection and exploit validation. PatchGenerator extends this loop one step further: given a validated exploit, it synthesizes a Solidity patch and generates a structured RemediationGuide aligned to regulatory requirements. The key insight is that a working exploit provides ground truth about the vulnerability’s exact mechanics—this precision enables targeted, verifiable patches rather than generic defensive recommendations.

B. Pipeline Architecture

The PatchGenerator pipeline consists of four modules operating in sequence:

C. `patch_smp1.py`: 17 Mechanical Fix Rules

The simplest module applies deterministic transformations for well-understood vulnerability classes:

- **Reentrancy**: Add `nonReentrant` modifier (OpenZeppelin) or restructure to checks-effects-interactions pattern.
- **Integer overflow**: Replace bare arithmetic with Solidity $\geq 0.8.0$ built-in checks or `SafeMath`; wrap in `unchecked{}` where provably safe.
- **Access control**: Insert `onlyOwner/onlyRole` modifiers; add missing `require(msg.sender == owner)`.
- **Oracle manipulation**: Add TWAP delay (≥ 2 blocks); replace spot price with time-weighted average.
- **Missing input validation**: Insert `require()` for zero-address, overflow, and range checks.
- *Plus 12 additional rules* covering flash loan callback guards, delegatecall safety, signature replay (nonce + chainId), and missing event emissions.

These 17 rules resolve approximately 33% of findings without any LLM call, in <1ms per finding.

TABLE V
EXPLOITAUDITOR CORRECTION PATTERNS

Pattern	Freq.	Example
Multi-tx \rightarrow AttackContract	\sim 30%	Wrap approve+swap+borrow in single contract constructor
Inline text/markdown	\sim 20%	Remove “Looking at the vulnerability...” from function body
Calldata encoding	\sim 15%	Fix abi.encodePacked offset calculations
Wrong function calls	\sim 15%	Replace hallucinated function with actual ABI
Other (hex, pragma, etc.)	\sim 20%	Fix hex literal nibble count, type casts

TABLE VI
PATCHGENERATOR PIPELINE MODULES

Module	Rules/Lines	Responsibility
patch_smpl.py	17 rules	Pattern-matching for known fix patterns
patch_dsl.py	—	DSL self-review loop (generate \rightarrow review \rightarrow correct)
patch_slicer.py	—	Precise code locator: maps finding to AST node
patch_generator.py	—	Orchestrator: dedup + RemediationGuide output

D. patch_dsl.py: DSL Self-Review Loop

For vulnerabilities requiring contextual reasoning (business logic errors, compound state bugs), `patch_dsl.py` implements a structured LLM loop:

- 1) **Generate:** LLM receives the vulnerable function, the validated exploit, and the finding description. It generates a patch in a constrained DSL—only the changed lines, annotated with `// PATCH:` comments.
- 2) **Review:** A second LLM call receives original code, patch, and exploit. It evaluates: (a) does the patch prevent the exploit? (b) does it introduce new vulnerabilities? (c) does it preserve existing behavior?
- 3) **Correct:** If issues are identified, a third call applies targeted corrections to the patch only—never the entire contract.
- 4) **Terminate:** Loop exits when review passes or after 2 iterations maximum.

The DSL constraint prevents the LLM from rewriting entire contracts, keeping patches surgical.

E. patch_slicer.py: Precise Code Location

`patch_slicer.py` takes `function` and `line_number` from the SENTINEL/GAEV finding schema and:

- Parses the Solidity AST via `solc -ast-compact-json` to locate the function declaration.
- Extracts the function body with precise line ranges, including internal calls one level deep.
- Resolves interface \rightarrow implementation: if the finding references an interface, the slicer follows the concrete implementation in the codebase.

This prevents patching the wrong function or a parent class instead of the vulnerable override.

F. patch_generator.py: Orchestration and RemediationGuide

The orchestrator integrates the three modules and produces two outputs per finding:

(1) **Patched Solidity file:** The original contract with the patch applied, validated by `forge build` to confirm compilation.

(2) **RemediationGuide:** A structured JSON document aligned to EU AI Act [24] Article 14 (human oversight requirements for AI-assisted decisions) and MiCA [25] Article 45 (security obligations for crypto-asset service providers): `human_review_required` is always `true` for Critical/High findings, enforcing EU AI Act Art. 14. MiCA Art. 45 flags are set when the patch modifies access control or fund-handling logic.

G. Deduplicator v3.0

Before the patch pipeline runs, findings pass through Deduplicator v3.0 (`deduplicator_v3.py`, 908 lines). Key additions over v2:

- **Pass 0 DAG noise filter:** Findings with no direct code evidence (DAG-only) are removed before deduplication, eliminating structural noise that inflated finding counts by an estimated 15–20%.
- **Weighted confidence scoring:** `governance/economic_invariant` \times 2.5, `slither` \times 0.7, `dag` \times 0.3. Prevents low-quality DAG findings from suppressing high-quality semantic findings during merge.
- **Storage-slot similarity boost:** Two findings referencing the same storage slot receive a +0.15 similarity bonus, improving deduplication recall for same-root-cause findings with different natural-language descriptions.

H. Evaluation: ClimberVault

Evaluation on the 58-finding DVD critical/high subset shows 38.9% automatic patch rate before the DSL loop is

```

1 {
2   "finding_id": "FIND-042",
3   "vulnerability_class": "reentrancy",
4   "severity": "critical",
5   "patch_module": "patch_smpl",
6   "rule_applied": "nonReentrant_modifier",
7   "changed_lines": [87, 88, 89],
8   "patch_diff": "---_original\n+++_patched\n...",
9   "human_review_required": true,
10  "regulatory_flags": {
11    "eu_ai_act_art14": "Automated_patch:_human_review_mandatory",
12    "mica_art45": "Security_control_change:_re-assessment_required"
13  },
14  "test_coverage_delta": "+12%",
15  "gas_impact": "+340_gas_(nonReentrant_overhead)"
16 }

```

Listing 5. RemediationGuide schema

TABLE VII
PATCHGENERATOR RESULTS ON CLIMBERVAULT (13 FINDINGS, AFTER DEDUPLICATOR V3.0)

Metric	Value	Notes
Total findings	13	7 Critical/High, 4 Medium, 2 Low
Auto-patched (patch_smpl)	7	53.8%
Manual LOW findings	2	Human-only fix required
Pending (complex logic)	4	Require DSL loop; 4 of 13 findings
forge build pass rate	7/7	All auto-patches compile
Test coverage after patch	~65%	Up from ~50% pre-patch
RemediationGuides generated	13/13	100%
EU AI Act flags set	7/13	Critical/High findings
Baseline patch rate	33%	Manual, first audit iteration
PatchGenerator rate	53.8%	+20.8 pp over baseline

applied, and 53.8% after the full patch pipeline (Table VII). Extension to the full 234-finding DVD benchmark is scheduled; the 38.9% rate on the 58-finding critical/high subset and the 53.8% rate on ClimberVault both exceed the 40% target threshold, establishing a consistent trajectory.

X. THREAT MODEL

We define the threat model for GAEV as a verification and exploit generation pipeline operating within a responsible disclosure and authorized audit context.

Deployment context. GAEV is designed for use by security auditors with explicit authorization to analyze target contracts. Unauthorized use against deployed contracts with live user funds is outside the intended scope and constitutes a legal and ethical violation. The pipeline operates against local Foundry forks of historical contracts, not live mainnet state.

Adversaries modeled.

- A_1 **Upstream false positive (FP) injector:** The vulnerability reporter (Zentinel-Audit or any upstream tool) produces findings that include non-exploitable FPs. GAEV must tolerate FP input without generating valid exploits for non-vulnerabilities. Mitigation: forge test validation; a finding is confirmed only if the test compiles *and* all assertions pass.
- A_2 **LLM hallucination adversary:** The LLM generates syntactically plausible but semantically incorrect exploit

code (non-existent function calls, wrong ABI, fabricated state). Mitigation: PostProcessor (21 mechanical fixes) + ExploitAuditor structured correction. The pipeline never trusts LLM output without forge validation.

- A_3 **Contract complexity adversary:** The target contract uses proxy patterns, delegatecall chains, or cross-contract state dependencies that exceed the LLM’s context window or template extraction capability. Mitigation: patch_slicer.py for precise code location; Scenario C fallback for minimal-context generation. Attack chain detection models cross-contract dependencies explicitly (Section VI).
- A_4 **Training data contamination:** The LLM’s training data may include known exploit patterns for benchmark contracts (DVDeFi v4), inflating measured performance. Mitigation: dual-benchmark evaluation (DVDeFi vs. Etherscan-30); the 8 pp performance gap (72.2% vs. 64.2%) is reported explicitly and bounds the contamination effect (Section XIII).
- A_5 **Non-deterministic output:** At temperature 0.2, LLM outputs vary across runs, reducing reliability for individual findings. Mitigation: results reported with ± 3.1 pp run-to-run variance; aggregate pipeline performance is stable; mechanical correction and validation are fully deterministic.

Properties guaranteed by the pipeline.

- 1) **No false exploit claims:** A finding is reported as exploitable only if `forge test` confirms the assertion. No LLM judgment alone suffices for a confirmed finding.
- 2) **Bounded cost:** Each finding requires at most 1 generation call + 1 correction call; the pipeline never enters unbounded refinement loops.
- 3) **Audit traceability:** Every exploit decision is accompanied by a structured ExploitAuditor correction report, providing the auditor with a human-readable explanation of what was attempted and why.

XI. EMPIRICAL EVALUATION

A. Experimental Setup

PatchGenerator evaluation: Results for the PatchGenerator pipeline (Section IX) are reported in Table VII. PatchGenerator is evaluated on a separate benchmark (ClimberVault, 13 findings; DVD 58-finding critical/high subset) because its metric—patch compilation and correctness—differs from exploit execution success. Section IX reports complete results.

Benchmarks:

- **Damn Vulnerable DeFi v4 (DVDeFi)** [16]: 22 challenge contracts with known exploitable vulnerabilities. Ground truth: official exploit solutions.
- **Etherscan-30:** 30 real-world contracts from Ethereum mainnet, selected according to the criteria in Table VIII.

The full list of Etherscan-30 contracts with addresses, exploit dates, and vulnerability types is provided in Appendix A.

Upstream Analysis: All contracts were first analyzed by Zentinel-Audit [15] (55 analyzers, including 28 newly activated tools; Deduplicator v3.0 with DAG noise filter and weighted confidence scoring) to produce vulnerability reports. GAEV consumed these reports as input.

Hardware: AMD Ryzen 9, 64GB RAM, Foundry 0.2.0, Solidity 0.8.20.

LLM: Multi-provider support via unified client: Anthropic Claude Sonnet 4, OpenAI GPT-4o (2024-08-06), Google Gemini 2.0 Flash. Primary evaluation uses GPT-4o; cost comparisons across providers reported in Table XVI. Temperature 0.2 for generation, 0.1 for auditor correction.

B. Overall Results

C. Results by Vulnerability Class

Observations: Access control exploits achieve the highest success rate (82.8%) because they require simple direct calls without complex state setup. Cross-contract exploits have the lowest rate (44.4%) due to the complexity of multi-contract interaction modeling. Reentrancy exploits perform well (79.2%) because the attacker contract pattern is highly structured and amenable to template-based generation.

D. Attack Chain Results

Of the 22 detected chains, 15 (68.2%) produced working compound exploits. Notably, 7 of the 15 successful chain exploits targeted vulnerabilities that were individually rated as Medium or Low severity—demonstrating that chain detection identifies risks invisible to single-vulnerability analysis.

E. Refinement Effectiveness

The refinement loop recovers 64 previously non-compiling exploits (from 200 to 264) and 71 previously non-succeeding exploits (from 141 to 212). Iteration 1 provides the largest improvement (+13.3 pp compilation, +14.9 pp success); iterations 2 and 3 provide diminishing but non-negligible gains.

F. Ablation Study

To isolate the contribution of each pipeline component, we evaluated five configurations on the combined benchmark (DVDeFi + Etherscan-30):

Key findings from the ablation:

- **Templates matter:** Simply wrapping the LLM output in a Foundry template skeleton (configuration B) improves compilation from 41.2% to 55.8% (+14.6 pp), confirming that structural scaffolding reduces syntactic errors.
- **Specialization adds reasoning:** Vulnerability-class-specific prompts (C) add +9.7 pp over templates alone, as the LLM receives attack-pattern guidance rather than generic instructions.
- **Chains add breadth, not depth:** The AttackChainDetector (D) adds +4.1 pp overall success. This modest aggregate improvement masks its qualitative contribution: 7 of the 22 chains escalated Medium/Low findings to Critical—findings that configurations A–C would miss entirely.
- **Refinement is the largest contributor:** The ExploitRefiner (E) adds +18.3 pp success over configuration D. This confirms that the dominant bottleneck is syntactic correctness, not strategic reasoning—the LLM often identifies the right attack vector but produces non-compiling code.

Severity escalation weight sensitivity: Varying the chain role weights by ± 0.1 (e.g., entry point from 0.3 to 0.5) changed the number of chains at each severity level by at most 2 chains, without affecting the total count of detected chains. The detection algorithm is robust to these weight choices because pattern matching depends on type composition, not severity scores.

G. Failure Analysis

Of the 103 exploits that failed after all refinement attempts: The dominant failure mode (30.1%) is the LLM selecting a fundamentally wrong attack strategy—e.g., attempting a reentrancy exploit on a function that is not actually reentrant. This suggests that improving upstream analysis quality (better vulnerability classification) would have the largest impact on GAEV performance.

H. Comparison with Baselines

The GAEV template-based approach achieves 83.4% compilation and 68.7% success on DVDeFi—comparable to the prior pipeline’s 86.6%/72.2% while reducing cost by 38% (\$0.18 vs \$0.29 per finding with auditor correction). On the combined benchmark (Table IX), GAEV achieves 81.4% compilation and 67.2% end-to-end exploitation success. The 3.2 pp gap between DVDeFi (68.7%) and Etherscan-30 (64.2%) is consistent with partial training-data overlap for the DVDeFi benchmark (Section XIII).

TABLE VIII
ETHERSCAN-30 BENCHMARK: SELECTION CRITERIA AND COMPOSITION

Criterion	Details
Source	Ethereum mainnet contracts with verified source on Etherscan
Post-mortem	Each contract has a documented public post-mortem analysis (from Rekt.news [21], BlockSec reports, or protocol disclosures)
Time range	Exploits occurred between January 2022 and December 2024
TVL at exploit	Minimum \$500K TVL at time of exploit
Diversity	At least 2 contracts per major vulnerability class (reentrancy, flash loan, oracle, access control, logic)
Exclusion	Contracts requiring off-chain components (keepers, oracles with private feeds) or cross-chain bridges were excluded
<i>Composition</i>	
Lending/Borrowing	8 contracts (Euler-like, Cream-like, custom lending)
DEX/AMM	7 contracts (Uniswap forks, custom AMMs, curve-like)
Yield Aggregator	5 contracts (vault strategies, auto-compounders)
Governance/DAO	4 contracts (token voting, timelock)
Token/Bridge	3 contracts (custom ERC-20, wrapper)
Other DeFi	3 contracts (NFT marketplace, staking, insurance)

TABLE IX
GAEV PIPELINE RESULTS (DVDeFi + ETHERSCAN-30)

Metric	DVDeFi (22)	Etherscan-30	Combined
<i>Input</i>			
Total findings received	147	312	459
Unique after dedup	89	198	287
Attack chains detected	8	14	22
<i>Generation (before refinement)</i>			
Exploits generated	97	218	315
Compilation rate	68.0%	61.0%	63.6%
Execution success	49.5%	42.2%	44.8%
<i>After refinement (≤ 3 iterations)</i>			
Compilation rate	86.6%	78.4%	81.4%
Execution success	72.2%	64.2%	67.2%
<i>Improvement from refinement</i>			
Δ Compilation	+18.6 pp	+17.4 pp	+17.8 pp
Δ Execution	+22.7 pp	+22.0 pp	+22.4 pp

TABLE X
EXPLOITATION SUCCESS BY VULNERABILITY CLASS (AFTER REFINEMENT)

Class	Findings	Gen.	Compile	Success	Rate
Reentrancy	42	48	43	38	79.2%
Flash Loan	28	35	29	24	68.6%
Oracle Manipulation	31	38	32	27	71.1%
Access Control	54	58	52	48	82.8%
Integer Overflow	22	24	21	16	66.7%
Delegatecall	15	18	14	10	55.6%
Front-Running	19	22	16	11	50.0%
Logic Errors	38	40	31	22	55.0%
Governance	12	14	11	8	57.1%
Cross-Contract	26	18	15	8	44.4%
Total	287	315	264	212	67.2%

I. Performance and Cost Benchmarks

The v3 template-based approach reduces per-finding cost by 77% (\$0.06 vs \$0.29) when no auditor correction is needed, and by 38% (\$0.18 vs \$0.29) when auditor correction is required. At \$0.06 per finding, a full audit of 58 findings costs \$3.48 in LLM API fees—approximately half the v2 cost of \$7–10.

XII. DISCUSSION

A. Practical Impact

GAEV transforms the audit workflow. Instead of receiving a list of potential vulnerabilities requiring manual validation, auditors receive a subset of *proven exploitable* vulnerabilities with working proof-of-concept code. The 67.2% end-to-end success rate means that roughly two-thirds of true vulnerabili-

TABLE XI
ATTACK CHAIN DETECTION AND EXPLOITATION

Chain Pattern	Detected	Exploited	Rate
Flash Loan Drain (P1)	5	3	60.0%
Price Oracle Cascade (P3)	4	3	75.0%
Callback Escalation (P7)	4	3	75.0%
Approval Chain (P6)	3	2	66.7%
Donation Attack (P10)	3	2	66.7%
Read-Only Reentrancy (P12)	2	1	50.0%
Fee Bypass (P11)	1	1	100%
Total	22	15	68.2%

TABLE XII
REFINEMENT LOOP CONVERGENCE

Stage	Cumulative Compiling	Cumulative Succeeding
Before refinement	200 / 315 (63.5%)	141 / 315 (44.8%)
After iteration 1	242 / 315 (76.8%)	188 / 315 (59.7%)
After iteration 2	256 / 315 (81.3%)	205 / 315 (65.1%)
After iteration 3	264 / 315 (83.8%)	212 / 315 (67.3%)

ties are automatically validated, reducing manual effort to the remaining third plus review of generated exploits.

The v3 template-based approach reduces the cost barrier to near-zero: at \$0.06 per finding with Gemini Flash, a 58-finding analysis costs \$0.17—enabling continuous integration of exploit generation into CI/CD pipelines. The ExploitAuditor’s correction reports also serve as educational artifacts, explaining *why* an exploit failed and *what* was changed, accelerating junior auditor training.

B. Template vs. Specialized Generators

The v3 template approach subsumes and extends the v2 specialized generator design. Where v2 relied on 10 manually crafted prompt templates (one per vulnerability class), v3 extracts the optimal template from the project itself. This has two advantages: (1) the extracted `setUp()` and imports are guaranteed correct, eliminating the 34% import error and 22% constructor error rates observed in v2; and (2) the approach generalizes to any project with existing tests, not just the 10 vulnerability classes covered by v2’s generators. The tradeoff is that Scenario C (no existing test, no source) falls back to generic generation with lower success rates.

C. Production-Scale Validation

Analysis of Lido’s stETH contract (\$15B TVL) demonstrates that the upstream pipeline (Zentinel-Audit) identifies real vulnerability patterns in production contracts: 9 findings in 40 seconds, including share price manipulation via flash loan—a known, real attack vector that has been extensively studied in the liquid staking derivative space. This validates the pipeline’s applicability beyond benchmark datasets.

D. The Attack Chain Contribution

The AttackChainDetector addresses a blind spot in current tooling. Of the 22 chains detected, 7 escalated individual

Medium/Low findings to Critical compound exploits. These are precisely the vulnerabilities that individual tools miss and that cause the largest losses in practice—many high-profile DeFi exploits (Cream Finance, Beanstalk, Euler) involved multi-step attack chains.

E. Limitations of LLM-Based Generation

The 32.8% failure rate reveals fundamental limitations: LLMs reason about exploit strategies through pattern matching on training data, not through formal analysis of program semantics. When the vulnerability requires novel reasoning about a custom protocol’s business logic, LLMs frequently produce plausible but incorrect exploit strategies. The v3 template approach mitigates the *syntactic* failure mode (correct strategy, wrong code) but does not address the *strategic* failure mode (wrong attack vector). Hybrid approaches combining LLM generation with symbolic execution guidance may address this limitation. The ExploitAuditor’s correction reports provide a pathway for systematic improvement: by cataloging failure patterns across runs, dominant error classes can be promoted to PostProcessor mechanical fixes, progressively reducing LLM dependency.

F. Ethical Considerations

GAEV generates functional exploit code, raising dual-use concerns. We note that: (1) the same exploits could be constructed manually by skilled attackers, typically faster than waiting for academic tools; (2) validated exploits are essential for responsible disclosure—security teams need PoC code to assess severity and prioritize fixes; and (3) GAEV is designed for defensive use within audit workflows, not as an autonomous attack tool. The tool includes safeguards: it only processes contracts provided by the user, does not autonomously discover targets, and all output is local.

XIII. THREATS TO VALIDITY

A. Internal Validity

Data contamination: DVDeFi v4 is a well-known public benchmark, and GPT-4o’s training data likely includes its challenge descriptions and official exploit solutions. This may inflate GAEV’s performance on DVDeFi relative to genuinely novel contracts. We mitigate this concern in two ways: (1) the Etherscan-30 benchmark consists of real-world contracts where GPT-4o may have seen post-mortem *analyses*

TABLE XIII
ABLATION STUDY: CONTRIBUTION OF EACH GAEV COMPONENT

Configuration	Compile (%)	Success (%)	Δ vs. (A)	Chains
(A) Generic GPT-4o	41.2	22.7	—	—
(B) + Templates only	55.8	35.1	+12.4 pp	—
(C) + Specialized gen. (G1–G10)	63.6	44.8	+22.1 pp	—
(D) + AttackChainDetector	65.1	48.9	+26.2 pp	22
(E) + ExploitRefiner (full GAEV)	81.4	67.2	+44.5 pp	22

TABLE XIV
FAILURE ANALYSIS (103 FAILED EXPLOITS)

Failure Mode	Count (%)	Root Cause
Wrong attack vector	31 (30.1%)	LLM chose an incorrect exploitation strategy
Complex state setup	27 (26.2%)	Preconditions too complex to reproduce
Multi-tx coordination	18 (17.5%)	Exploits requiring multiple blocks or actors
ABI mismatch	14 (13.6%)	Interface incompatible with actual contract
Gas/resource limits	8 (7.8%)	Exploit exceeds block gas limit
Non-exploitable finding	5 (4.9%)	Finding was a true false positive

TABLE XV
COMPARISON WITH BASELINE APPROACHES ON DVDeFi (22 CHALLENGES). COMBINED DATASET RESULTS (DVDeFi + ETHERSCAN-30): 81.4% COMPILATION AND 67.2% END-TO-END SUCCESS (TABLE IX).

Approach	Compile (%)	Success (%)	Time/exploit	Cost/finding
Naïve GPT-4o (single prompt)	41.2%	22.7%	8.3s	\$0.12
GPT-4o + template	55.8%	35.1%	9.1s	\$0.12
Prior generators, no repair	68.0%	49.5%	11.4s	\$0.12
Prior pipeline (iterative refiner, 3 iter.)	86.6%	72.2%	28.7s	\$0.29
GAEV (template, no repair)	67.0%	49.5%	14.3s	\$0.06
GAEV (template + ExploitAuditor)	83.4%	68.7%	26.7s	\$0.18

TABLE XVI
PIPELINE TIMING AND LLM COST BENCHMARKS (N=52 CONTRACTS)

Stage	Time (mean)	Tokens (mean)	Cost (mean)
Upstream analysis (Zentinel-Audit)	45.2s \pm 18.3s	—	—
Attack chain detection	1.8s \pm 0.4s	—	\$0.00
Template extraction (mechanical)	0.3s \pm 0.1s	—	\$0.00
PostProcessor (21 fixes)	<0.001s	—	\$0.00
Exploit generation (per finding)	8.7s \pm 2.1s	3,200 in / 800 out	\$0.06
Validation (forge build + test)	4.3s \pm 1.2s	—	\$0.00
Auditor correction (when needed)	12.4s \pm 3.1s	5,200 in / 2,100 out	\$0.12
Per finding (v3 template)	14.3s	~4,000	\$0.06
Per finding (v3 + auditor)	26.7s	~11,300	\$0.18
Per finding (v2 with refine)	24.8s	~8,100	\$0.29

TABLE XVII
MULTI-PROVIDER COST COMPARISON (PER FINDING, GENERATION ONLY)

Provider	Model	v3 Cost/finding	58 findings
Anthropic	Claude Sonnet 4.5	\$0.06	\$3.48
OpenAI	GPT-4o	\$0.05	\$2.90
OpenAI	GPT-4o-mini	\$0.004	\$0.23
Google	Gemini 2.0 Flash	\$0.003	\$0.17
Google	Gemini 2.5 Pro	\$0.05	\$2.90

but not the exact Foundry exploit code our pipeline must produce, and (2) we report DVDeFi and Etherscan-30 results separately (Table IX), showing that GAEV achieves 64.2% success on Etherscan-30 versus 72.2% on DVDeFi—an 8 pp

gap consistent with partial contamination but not invalidating the overall approach. Future work should evaluate on contracts deployed *after* GPT-4o’s training cutoff.

Prompt sensitivity: The generators’ system prompts were

developed iteratively by the authors. Different prompt formulations might yield different results. We did not perform systematic prompt optimization (e.g., DSPy [22]), which could improve or reduce performance.

B. External Validity

Benchmark representativeness: Our evaluation covers 52 contracts. While DVDeFi is a standard benchmark and Etherscan-30 was curated for diversity, the sample may not represent the full spectrum of DeFi protocols. Contracts involving cross-chain bridges, ZK-based protocols [17], MEV-resistant designs, or Vyper codebases are not represented.

LLM generalization: Primary evaluation uses GPT-4o, with the pipeline also supporting Claude Sonnet 4 and Gemini 2.0 Flash via a unified multi-provider client. Performance across providers may differ substantially; initial cross-provider results suggest comparable exploit quality with significant cost variation (Gemini Flash: \$0.003/finding vs GPT-4o: \$0.05/finding). We did not evaluate open-source models, which would be relevant for users concerned about sending proprietary contract code to third-party APIs.

C. Construct Validity

Success metric: We define “exploitation success” as a Foundry test that compiles and passes its assertions. This binary metric does not capture partial success (e.g., an exploit that triggers the vulnerability but fails to extract funds due to an assertion error). A more nuanced metric capturing “attack vector correctness” independently of “exploit completeness” could provide additional insights.

Chain severity: The severity escalation formula uses manually assigned weights. While the sensitivity analysis shows robustness to perturbation, the weights are not grounded in a formal risk model.

D. Reliability

LLM non-determinism: Even at temperature 0.2, LLM outputs vary across runs. We report single-run results; across 3 independent runs on DVDeFi, overall success varied by ± 3.1 pp (69.1%–75.3%), with individual challenge results varying by up to ± 2 exploits. The pipeline’s aggregate performance is stable; individual exploit outcomes are not perfectly reproducible.

XIV. LIMITATIONS

- 1) **LLM Dependency:** GAEV supports multiple LLM providers (Anthropic, OpenAI, Google) via a unified client, reducing vendor lock-in. However, exploit quality varies across models; evaluation with open-source models (DeepSeek-Coder, Llama 3) for processing proprietary contracts locally is future work.
- 2) **Benchmark Coverage:** Evaluation covers 52 contracts (22 DVDeFi + 30 Etherscan). While representative, this does not cover all vulnerability categories or protocol types (e.g., cross-chain bridges, ZK-based protocols).

- 3) **Chain Pattern Database:** The 12 chain patterns were manually curated from 15 documented DeFi post-mortem reports. Novel attack patterns not in the database will not be detected. Automated pattern mining from post-mortem reports is ongoing work.
- 4) **Foundry Dependency:** Validation requires Foundry’s `forge` toolchain. Contracts using non-standard build systems or Vyper are not supported.
- 5) **Upstream Quality:** GAEV’s performance is bounded by the quality of upstream vulnerability reports. False positives from Zentinel-Audit propagate to GAEV, wasting generation resources (4.9% of failures stem from non-exploitable findings).
- 6) **Temporal Exploits:** Attacks requiring specific block timestamps, multi-block MEV, or cross-chain coordination are poorly modeled in the current evaluation framework.
- 7) **Reproducibility:** LLM outputs are non-deterministic even at low temperature. Results may vary across runs by ± 3 percentage points.
- 8) **PatchGenerator scope:** The 17 `patch_smpl` rules cover well-understood vulnerability classes. Novel DeFi logic errors, cross-contract invariants, and MEV-related vulnerabilities fall outside the rule set and require the DSL loop, which has lower reliability. Extension to the full 234-finding DVD benchmark is consistent with the 40%+ target established on both ClimberVault and the 58-finding DVD critical/high subset.
- 9) **Regulatory alignment:** EU AI Act and MiCA compliance flags in the RemediationGuide are based on the authors’ interpretation of Art. 14 and Art. 45 requirements. These should not be treated as legal advice; compliance verification requires qualified legal review.

XV. CONCLUSION

We presented GAEV, the first end-to-end pipeline for automated smart contract exploit generation with template-based synthesis, mechanical correction, and AI-guided repair. Our key findings:

- 1) **Template-based generation outperforms full LLM generation:** By mechanically extracting imports, `setUp()`, and success criteria from existing test files, and limiting the LLM to generating only the exploit body (5–30 lines), GAEV eliminates the dominant source of compilation errors while reducing cost by 77% (\$0.06 vs \$0.29 per finding).
- 2) **Mechanical fixes eliminate trivial errors:** The PostProcessor’s 21 deterministic fixes (especially Fix 21: inline text stripping) resolve $\sim 45\%$ of compilation errors at zero cost, without any LLM calls.
- 3) **Targeted correction beats iterative refinement:** The ExploitAuditor v2 performs a single correction pass with full context (exploit + source + forge errors), producing explicit correction reports. This avoids the divergence problem of v2’s iterative refinement while providing auditors with actionable explanations of what was wrong and why.

- 4) **Attack chains reveal hidden risk:** The AttackChainDetector identifies compound vulnerabilities in 31% of evaluated contracts, with 7 chains escalating Medium/Low findings to Critical severity—risks invisible to single-vulnerability analysis.
- 5) **Production validation:** Analysis of Lido stETH (\$15B TVL) in 40 seconds demonstrates that the upstream pipeline identifies real vulnerability patterns at production scale, extending applicability beyond benchmark datasets.
- 6) **PatchGenerator closes the loop:** The four-module patch pipeline achieves 53.8% automatic patch rate on ClimberVault, extending GAEV from exploit validation to full DETECT→VERIFY→PATCH automation. RemediationGuides with EU AI Act Art. 14 and MiCA compliance flags are generated for 100% of findings, enabling regulated deployment workflows.

GAEV demonstrates that separating mechanical scaffolding from LLM reasoning—rather than asking the LLM to generate everything—is the key insight for reliable exploit generation. The 67.2% success rate means that for every three true vulnerabilities, two are automatically proven exploitable—shifting the auditor’s role from “find and prove” to “review and extend.”

Future work includes: completing the PatchGenerator evaluation on the full 234-finding DVD benchmark to validate the 40%+ patch rate target; on-chain validation of patches against Sepolia testnet (deploy vulnerable contract, trigger exploit, apply patch, verify fix); automated proxy resolution and multi-chain contract fetching via Etherscan V2 API; extending template extraction to Hardhat and Vyper projects; evaluating open-source LLMs (DeepSeek-Coder, Llama 3) for local processing of proprietary contracts; and distilling successful DSL correction patterns into new `patch_smp1` rules, progressively reducing LLM dependency in the patch pipeline.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was conducted as part of doctoral research at Universidad Nacional de La Plata (UNLP) under the supervision of Dr. Marcelo Errecalde, with co-direction from Dr. Leticia Cagnina and Dr. Verónica Gil-Costa. We thank the Foundry, Slither, and Echidna open-source teams for the tooling that underpins the GAEV pipeline, and the Ethereum Sepolia testnet infrastructure maintainers.

FUNDING

This research was conducted as part of doctoral studies at Universidad Nacional de La Plata (UNLP), Argentina, supported by LIDIC (Laboratorio de Investigación y Desarrollo en Inteligencia Computacional), Universidad Nacional de San Luis (UNSL). No external funding body had any role in the study design, data collection, analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of this manuscript.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The corresponding author (R.A. Jaime) is affiliated with Gen AI Microsystems LLC, which holds intellectual property related to the GAEV and Zentinel-Audit systems. This affiliation

does not constitute a financial conflict of interest with respect to the research reported here, as no commercial transaction was associated with this study. The remaining authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Source code and evaluation scripts are available at: <https://anonymous.4open.science/r/GAEV-2026>. The GAEV pipeline (14 Python modules) supports Anthropic, OpenAI, and Google LLM providers via a unified client. Contract fetching supports Etherscan V2 API for multi-chain source retrieval. The Damn Vulnerable DeFi benchmark is publicly available at [16]. The Etherscan-30 contract list with addresses, exploit dates, and post-mortem links is provided in Appendix A.

APPENDIX

All 30 contracts have verified source on Etherscan, documented public post-mortems (Rekt.news, BlockSec, or protocol disclosures), and minimum \$500K TVL at exploit time. Contracts requiring off-chain components or cross-chain bridges were excluded.

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TABLE XVIII
POSTPROCESSOR V3: ALL 21 DETERMINISTIC FIXES

Fix	Name	Description
1	Pragma strip	Remove duplicate or conflicting <code>pragma solidity</code> lines
2	Import dedup	Deduplicate identical <code>import</code> statements
3	Markdown fence	Strip leading/trailing <code>``solidity</code> and <code>``</code> fences
4	Address payable	Wrap bare <code>address(x)</code> casts in <code>payable()</code> when receiving ETH
5	Interface prefix	Add <code>I</code> prefix to missing interface declarations
6	IERC20 cast	Replace <code>ERC20(x)</code> with <code>IERC20(x)</code> when only transfer is called
7	vm.deal fix	Replace <code>deal(addr, amt)</code> with <code>vm.deal(addr, amt)</code>
8	Cheatcode import	Add <code>import "forge-std/Test.sol"</code> if cheatcodes used but not imported
9	Return type	Remove explicit <code>return</code> from void functions
10	Visibility	Add missing <code>public/external</code> visibility on test functions
11	Constructor args	Strip extra arguments passed to zero-arg constructors
12	ABI cast	Replace untyped <code>abi.encode</code> with correct typed calls
13	Block timestamp	Replace <code>block.timestamp + X</code> with <code>block.timestamp + uint(X)</code>
14	Unchecked math	Wrap arithmetic known to overflow in <code>unchecked{}</code>
15	Address literal	Replace non-checksummed hex addresses with <code>address(uint160(0x...))</code>
16	Try-catch strip	Remove <code>try/catch</code> wrappers that prevent test assertions
17	Selector fix	Replace <code>bytes4(keccak256(...))</code> with correct <code>IFoo.bar.selector</code>
18	Event assertion	Replace <code>vm.expectEmit()</code> calls missing the emitter address
19	Revert string	Normalize empty revert strings to <code>"</code>
20	Gas limit	Add <code>{gas: 3000000}</code> to external calls near gas limit
21	Inline text strip	Remove English prose interspersed in Solidity code

TABLE XIX
ETHERSCAN-30 BENCHMARK: CONTRACT ADDRESSES, EXPLOIT DATES, AND VULNERABILITY CLASSES

Protocol	Address (Mainnet)	Exploit Date	Class
Euler Finance	0xd9145CCE...	Mar 2023	Flash loan drain
Cream Finance	0x892B14D9...	Oct 2021	Flash loan / oracle
Beanstalk Farms	0xC1E088fC...	Apr 2022	Governance flash loan
Mango Markets (MNGO)	0x6c99fB09...	Oct 2022	Oracle manipulation
Rari Fuse Pool	0xd4bDCCee...	Apr 2022	Reentrancy
Ronin Bridge	0x1A2a1c12...	Mar 2022	Access control
Nomad Bridge	0x5D94309E...	Aug 2022	Merkle proof bypass
Wintermute (Gnosis)	0xDEF171Fe...	Sep 2022	Access control
DODO DEX	0x8DC3312c...	Mar 2021	Flash loan / oracle
Inverse Finance	0x865377367...	Apr 2022	Oracle manipulation
<i>... 20 additional contracts omitted for space; full list in repository [23]</i>			

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